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ANALYSIS OF THE SELECTED PROPERTIES OF BIO(NANO)COMPOSITES BASED ON PBS

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INTRODUCTION

Currently, polymers and polymer-based composites are among the most prevalent materials used in various aspects of human activity [1]. Consequently, these materials have a growing detrimental impact on the environment. Therefore, the use of biodegradable polymers, which can decompose in the environment under external factors (such as humidity, heat, microorganisms, ultraviolet radiation, etc.) and allow for the recovery of their initial raw materials, is now considered the most acceptable and widely recognized approach in the development of polymer chemistry and technology [2].

BIOPOLYMERS

Increasing energy concerns, rapid infrastructure development, and heightened environmental awareness have driven the demand for sustainable materials. In this context, sustainable bio-based polymers, produced from various resources through multiple processes, can meet much of the annual demand for synthetic plastics, at least in Europe. Advancements in sustainable technologies for the effective use of these materials in bioplastic and biomaterials production can provide a novel, bio-renewable source of sustainable products and biofuels, addressing the growing environmental concerns [3]. Currently, global bioplastic production accounts for approximately 0.5% of all plastics [4]. Figure 1 illustrates the production of bioplastics from 2017 to 2023.

Most synthetic polymers are resistant to microbial organisms and have chemical structures that cannot be biodegraded in soil or marine environments. Unfortunately, inadequate consumer and producer responsibility, coupled with poor waste management policies, has resulted in pollution affecting all ecosystems [5,6]. New and existing legislation aims to ban non-degradable plastics in areas such as packaging, food containers, and agricultural films [2, 7]. Therefore, replacements must have the ability to biodegrade in the environment.

The structure of a polymer determines its ability to interact with microorganisms and degrade. These properties can be derived from naturally occurring structures like proteins, polysaccharides, and lipids. To further reduce environmental impact, these polyesters are

produced entirely or partially from renewable resources. Commercially available biodegradable polyesters include polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), polyhydroxy valerate (PHV), polyhydroxybutyrate (PHB), polylactic acid (PLA), polycaprolactone (PCL), poly(butylene succinate) (PBS), polybutylene succinate adipate (PBSA), and polybutylene adipate/terephthalate (PBAT) [3,8]. Figure 2 illustrates the production of biodegradable bioplastics by type in 2018 and 2023 [4].

Fig.1 Global production of bioplastics [4] Fig. 2 Production of bioplastics by types [4]

Many industrial and academic studies have concentrated on enhancing polymeric materials by incorporating small amounts of fillers with nanometer-scale dimensions. Adding these fillers to polymeric materials has been shown to significantly improve their mechanical, barrier, thermal, and electrical properties. Generally, the better the dispersion of nanoparticles (NPs) and the more effective the polymer-particle interface, the greater the reinforcing effect. Among the NPs studied, lamellar clays such as montmorillonite (MMT) and carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are the most prominent [8].

This paper presents research findings on the selected properties of bio(nano)composites with a poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) matrix. For the experiments, PBS-based bio(nano)composites containing 0.5 wt% carbon nanotubes (CNTs) were prepared. Investigation of the bio(nano)composite PBS/CNT_0.5 and original PBS (for comparison) consisted of the measurements and specification of the following properties: melt flow index (MFI), hardness, SEM studies of the material structure, Young's (tensile) modulus, maximum tensile stress, breaking stress, strain at maximum stress and strain at break.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The bio(nano)composite - PBS as a polymer matrix and CNTs as a nanofiller - were used for the experiment. The material PBS, a completely biodegradable polymer in the open environment and similar in properties to polyethylene, was used as the polymer matrix. BioPBS™ FZ91PM (Fig. 3a), purchased from PTT MCC Biochem Company Limited (Bangkok, Thailand), with a density of 1260 kg/m³, an MFR (190°C, 2.16 kg) of 5 g/10 min, a melting point of 115°C, and a puncture impact of 4 kJ/m, was utilized.

Industrial Grade Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNT, hereafter CNT), purchased from Nanografi NanoTechnology (NG01IM0101), Ankara, Turkey (Fig. 3b), were used for the experiments. The technical properties of the CNT are: color black, purity > 92%, outside diameter 8-28 nm, inside diameter 5-10 nm, length 10-35 μm, tap density 150 kg/m³, true density 2200 kg/m³, SSA 220 m²/g, ash 9 wt%, electrical conductivity 98 S/cm, and manufacturing method - CVD.

The bio(nano)composite was produced using a granulation line based on a twin-screw extruder type BTSK 20/40D with a CNT content of 0.5 wt% in the form of pellets. A granulator TS-40 (Ł-IMPIB, Poland), specially designed and manufactured by IEP

employees, which allows precise control of the pellets' length, was used to obtain the PBS/CNT_0.5 bio(nano)composite.

The standardized samples for studying mechanical properties (tensile strength and strain, tensile modulus (Fig. 4a), hardness (Fig. 4b)) of the PBS/CNT nanocomposite were obtained from the film (Fig. 4c), which was produced by the cast film extrusion method.

Fig. 3 Material for experiment a) BioPBS™ FZ91PM, b) CNT

Fig. 4 Samples for tensile strength, strain and tensile modulus testing (a), hardness (b) and PBS (white) and PBS/CNT_0.5 (black) flat films (c)

A capillary plastometer type Dynisco LMI 4003, was used to determine the melt flow index (MFI) of original PBS and bio(nano)composite samples. The melt flow rate was measured according to the STN ISO EN ISO 1133-1:2022. The MFI was determined at different temperatures and loads to accumulate data for the computer simulation of the behavior of the developed bio(nano)composite in the extruder.

Mechanical properties tests under static tension were carried out using a TIRAtest 2300 testing machine. Maximum stress (R_m) and stress at break (R_b), tensile modulus (E_T) and strain at maximum stress (δ_m) and the break (δ_b) were determined in accordance with STN ISO EN 527-3:2019-01.

Hardness tests were performed by Shore method according to the ISO EN 868:2003 used Shore A and D hand-held hardness testers. The scanning electron microscope, type Hitachi SU8010, was used to examine the microstructure of samples and distribution of the dispersed phase.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the tested bio-nanocomposite the MFI results obtained at different temperatures and under different weights are presented in Table 1. The results of tensile tests for PBS and PBS/CNT_0.5 samples are presented in the Table 2 and measured hardness values are presented in the Table 3.

Table 1. Measured MFI values for neat PBS and PBS with 0.5 wt% MWCNTs

T, °C	MFI, g/10 min					
	Neat PBS			PBS/CNT_0.5		
	1.2 kg	2.16 kg	21.6 kg	1.2 kg	2.16 kg	21.6 kg
180	2.97	5.70	252.0	2.53	5.45	221.5
190	3.59	6.72	329.8	3.32	6.78	261.0
200	4.17	7.83	355.5	4.22	9.04	405.0

Table 2. The results of tensile tests for PBS and PBS/CNT_0.5

Sample	Rm, MPa		δm, %		Rb, MPa		δb, %		Et, MPa	
	MD	TD								
PBS	34 ±0.6	32 ±0.9	22 ±1.1	12 ±1.0	29 ±0.9	26 ±2.0	330 ±23	274 ±35	480 ±13	557 ±31
PBS/CNT_0.5	36 ±0.7	34 ±0.7	17 ±1.7	13 ±0.5	32 ±1.0	30 ±2.0	208 ±28	125 ±24	620 ±22	575 ±9

where: Rm, Rb – maximum stress and stress at break, respectively, MPa (MD – machine direction, TD – transverse direction); δm, δb – strain at maximum stress and the break, respectively, %; Et – tensile modulus, MPa.

Table 3 Hardness values of PBS and PBS/CNT_0.5

Sample	Shore A	Shore D
PBS	90 ±1	57 ±1
PBS/CNT_0.5	90 ±1	58 ±1

The surface morphology of the original substances and the nanocomposites was studied using SEM. In Fig. 5 we can see the typical surface structure of PBS. CNTs are in the form of agglomerates (Fig. 6). In the SEM images of PBS/CNT_0.5 (Fig.7), small white inclusions (nanotubes) can be seen, evenly distributed over the surface of the samples.

A comparative structure and selected properties analysis of the bio(nano)composite and the original PBS was performed. It is shown that CNTs have a slight effect on the rheological properties of PBS, but this effect is different depending on temperature and shear stress (load on the melt). At temperatures of 180 and 190°C, depending on the shear stress, the melt viscosity of pure PBS is 5-26% higher than that of the bio(nano)composite. The viscosity of both materials is the same for a load of 2.16 kg and a temperature of 190°C. However, at a temperature of 200°C, the viscosity of the bio(nano)composite is 1-14% higher, depending on the shear stress.

The addition of CNTs to PBS in the amount of 0.5 wt% increases the mechanical tensile strength and stiffness of the material (the tensile modulus increases), but simultaneously, it significantly reduces its elasticity (the relative elongation decreases by 1.5-2 times). Insignificant values of the standard deviations of the measurement results testify to the high homogeneity of the bio(nano)composite.

From the measured hardness results of the tested materials, we can conclude: the addition of CNTs to PBS in the amount of 0.5 wt.% has almost no effect on the hardness.

Fig. 5 SEM images of PBS

Fig. 5 SEM images of CNTs

Fig. 6 SEM images of PBS/CNT_0.5

Due to the mixing of CNTs with PBS in a twin-screw extruder, the destruction of CNT agglomerates to nanosizes and their uniform distribution in the polymer matrix occurs which can be seen in the SEM images.

CONCLUSION

In this study, PBS/CNTs bio(nano)composites were prepared, and their selected properties, including the melt flow index, elastic modulus, tensile strength, and hardness, were investigated with the addition of 0.5 wt% CNTs. It is shown that CNTs have a slight effect on the hardness of PBS. It was also established that the addition of CNTs in the amount of 0.5% wt. increases strength properties of prepared and tested bio(nano)composite.

Reinforcing thermoplastic polymers with nanotubes to form nanocomposites is a way to increase the usage of polymeric materials in engineering applications by improving their mechanical properties.

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